

RECOGNIZING CUSTOMER COMPLAINT BEHAVIOR IN A RESTAURANT

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ABSTRACT

Customer complaining behavior (CCB) which deals with analysis of all the aspects involved in the customers reactions towards a product or a service failure. Customer satisfaction, dissatisfaction and complaint behavior are highly correlated and obvious subjects which are investigated by customer studies and marketing. Now a days, at the origin of these studies we can consider the real marketing problems. The purpose of this paper is to determine the effect of attitude, loyalty and politeness on customer complaining behavior in a restaurant. A questionnaire was designed by using scales to see the reactions of respondents. Adults filled One hundred and fifty questionnaires and regression was used to scrutinize the relation between attitude, loyalty, politeness and their complaining behavior. The results show that complaint and complaining behavior has a positive correlation and customer loyalty is meaningfully allied with customer complaining behavior. Customer complaining behavior is directly affected by attitude. Moreover, the use of voice and third-party action as complaining behavior decreases as the drift of politeness increases and the use of private action uncorrelated with the drift to be polite. According to the results, managers should focus on customer's attitude and positive politeness through which complaining behavior can be decreased.

Keywords: Attitude, Politeness, Loyalty, Private actions, Voice response, Negative word of mouth, Complaint,

PAPER TYPE-Research paper

INTRODUCTION

Though in the 1970s the study of complaining behavior begins but it is still applicable in business & academic research. This helps to initiate a marketing philosophy in management and complaint handling of satisfaction as well as to dissatisfaction. Some learning measured that the response submits to the various way of the experiencing criticism (Westbrook 1987). The most delegate role to hypothesis is from Singh (1988), who explain complaining behavior is a collection of behavioral and non-behavioral response resultant from differentiated displeasure in a shopping or expenditure event.

Consumption evaluation process can be defined as the paradigm of conformation or disconfirmation (Churchill and Suprenant, 1982). The conformation, which contributes to satisfaction, realize in situation where the product meets the expectation the customer. While disconfirmation realizes in situations where there is a negative deference between the previous expectation and performance of product (Donoghue and Deklerk, 2006). Dissatisfaction arising from the evaluation of the purchase expectation may result in complaint (Snellmamann and vihtkari, 2003; kau and serene, 1995). In other words the more complaints the lesser the satisfaction would be (ali et.al. 2010). Complaint as one of the method used in ordered to express customer dissatis-

faction makes up the starting point of complaint behaviours. (Singh, 1988) Customer complaint behaviors is combination Of different responses a few or all of which are trigger by the displeasure. New investigate shows that dissatisfied consumer show direct behavior such as negative opinion and quit rather than complaint straight to the organization (tschol et al., 1994). They may analyze the cause of this satisfaction and identify opportunity for progress. Past research has assessed complaining behavior with regard to the extent of consumer engagement in the negative word of mouth and voicing, particularly as related to various individual traits and severity of services failure (day and bodur, 1978 villarreal-camacho, 1983 bolting 1989, blodget and tax, 1993) complaints to third parties come from customers who have not found to know the problem to the more severe, bearing in mind that their displeasure is not an isolated case and may involve other customer (Hogarth et al, 2001). This refers indirect behavior adjust at avoid status of dissatisfaction for the customer to other. Complaints usually been regard as negative response displeased people and the organization had planned to stop or cut them to minimum extent. But new concept concenter negative responses as helpful advice and it is not necessary indicator of poor performance" (Phau and Sari, 2004. 407) the complaint unable firm to turn into alert of problem in services and become able to recover their act wisely. The wise response "Can increase customer loyalty

and satisfy the customer". (Oh 2006 P60). When customer don't transfer complaint to firm, not only the chance of determining and solving problem is lost, but also same negative result occurs for both company and customer like changing firm, applying legal action, compiling to public and private bodies etc. (Davidow and dacin 1997). Therefore understanding the factor that effect customer propensity to complain to firm is necessary for this success of firm.

From the point of customer, it is asserted that no complain propensity to firm resulted from not knowing to complain to whom, the idea of not taking into consideration of problem by firm appropriately, rude, accusatory behavior of employs and pervious negative experience etc. In addition to these, customer compiling more difficult then leaving the firm and the think response of complaint is given to late if return complain is perform (Whitely, 1995). Pervious study investigates the propensity to complain in term of customer. Present study argues the effect of situational factor of complain tendency namely perceived dissatisfaction, customer loyalty, expiation from compiling process and attribute about source of problem. The general purposes of current study in explore the factor that effect the complaint behaviour in different situation. More specifically the study will try to achieve the following objectives.

- To understand the relationship between complaint and complaining behavior.
- To understand the role of loyalty in the complaining behavior.
- The effect of attitude on the complaining behavior.
- To find out whether or not politeness would affect the complaining behavior.

Research questions a developed to obtain appropriate information that is require fulfilling the research objective. This research study attempts to answer the following questions.

- Is there any relationship between complain and compiling behaviour?
- How loyalties help to understand the complaining behavior?
- How these variables influence the complaining behavior?
- Did the politeness affect the complaining behavior?

LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH MODEL

Below is the abstract border for complaining behavior use to define the build and identify the most relevant variable purposed in literature to explain its origin.

CUSTOMER COMPLAINING BEHAVIOR

In 1988 According to Singh complaining behavior of the Customer is a place of multiple responses. It also show that customer complaining attitude effect the complaining behavior (grace et.al 2006) and that culture difference effect attitude the complaining behavior (coates et al.,2010). Mcdougall et al.,(2000) recommended that all consumer would remain loyal to the service provide even when a services crash is not solve. customer decide to do nothing because the complain will not result in favourable outcome or the cost of complaining are to high (Blodgett et.al,2006). The consumer choose to do nothing and forget about the dissatisfying experience (kim et al.,2010). Singh (1990) call these customer passive and (panther22004) identified as "upset no action" yuksel et.al (2006 chose to follow Hirschman 1970) and conceptualized "no action" as loyalty.

Hirschman (1970) conceptualized voice can help out to change any type of un pleasant behaviour. Conceptualized general protest addressed to anyone who care to listen (panther22004 naus at al 2007). The most voice that's we use is direct complain. This type of complaining behavior help out to increase the efficiency of the services that is provided and the complaining will decrease and helpful in service recovery. Third party complaining includes complaining to industry bodies, regularity bodies, government agency and consumer group (Singh 1988). Negative opinion in public and taking action outside. Relationship is growing in importance as consumer have become empowered with now tool to cost effectively communicate with a wider audience and potentially inform other ordamage a brand (Blodgedd et al 2006 ward 2006 gregoire et al 2009). Private response include word of mouth comments and change behavior with the recent addition of web site communication (Blodget 2et al 2006) complaining behavior is a driven by the type and level of service failure the effectiveness of recovery process the strength of the relationship and other factor related to the dissatisfactory situation (Mittal et al 2008)

CUSTOMER LOYALTY

The concept of loyalty is usually expressed by such words like dedication, commitment, reliability, stability, patience and it is used in subject like sport team, family member, faith etc. furthermore using income that earned in difficult conditions, for purchasing certain products or by purchasing certain company is called as customer loyalty Brooks, 2010. Loyalty is a passive response, that indicates the member care about the relationship with the service provider and therefore tries to find reason to the remain in the service relationship (Evanschitzky et al, 2011). The loyal customer

concept is that dissatisfaction from the service failure in the hope that things will improve in the future. Loyalty is psychological barriers to exit that may give the service organization a chance to retain their best customers despite service failure (panther and Farquhar,2004). In marketing literature the role of effective complain management on customer loyalty is a current subject. In this context yapping, shoaling and Xing (2009) researcher affects of service recovery (explaining, communication, feedback and redress) on perceived justice and customer loyalty. In the other hand the effect of customer loyalty on complaint behavior is not taken similar attention fornell and Werner felt (1988). Asselt that loyal customer who experienced dissatisfaction tend to complain of more often then non loyal (fornell and Werner, 1988). It can b claimed that loyal customer prefer to solve their problems wth firm instead of leaving firm immediately (oztopcu, 2006). Forman 6research by blogett and grandois (1992) introduces the construct from hirschman (1970) suggested that loyal customer should be more likely to complain less likely to exit to do negative word of mouth when they satisfied with a product. Another research also revealed that public library user “who think themselves loyal to the library are less likely to complain to third party, (oh 2004). Based in this it is hypothesize that

H1. Complaining behavior is meaningful related with customer loyalty.

ATTITUDE

Can be termed as subjective belief in authority of a dissatisfied customers' obtaining compensation from the company (Richins, 1987).In the time of intense competition, not only service firms but also destination try to reach and hold a pool of loyal and advantageous visitors by providing 'socks Knocking' service (Anderson et al., 2007). However, mistakes are normal occurrence in service businesses, above all tourism and hospitality settings (Avci et al., 2003). Thus, firms need to be set to offer useful and capable solution. For this reason, first they need to know how members of their goal market think and behave, in other words, what are their attitude towards complaining (Oh, et al., 2006).a number of researchers have postulate that attitudes toward complaining (personal Norms and/or societal benefits) influence complaint responses with voices and negative word-of-mouth (Richins et al., 1982). “consumers who have a more caring manner towards complaining maybe because they are confident of success, or because they would not think mostly painful in making a complaint are more likely to complain than those who have a harmful attitude towards register their dissatisfaction” (Bodey and Grace, 2007, p. 187). Likewise, Cho and Joung, (1999) interpret feelings towards complaining as attitude towards right seeking where they found a strong relationship between attitudes and actual right seeking. Similarly, Richins (1982) support the relationship be-

tween 'Attitude toward right seeking' and 'right seeking intention'. Blodgett et al. (1995) put forward that consumers who are averse to right seeking will just silently leave and or connect in negative word-of-mouth behavior. On the other hand, attitude to complaining was linked to one's intention or behavior to complain in other words, normally, consumers with a more positive attitude towards complaining have a greater tendency to complain (grace et al., 2007)

H2: attitude has a direct effect on complaining behavior.

CUSTOMER POLITENESS

Several act are essentially intimidating to look and so need softening. Politeness make out as a variable style to maintain the listener face. the positive social value a person effectively claims for himself is face Brown and Levinson (1987) there are two kind of faces. Positive face concern that have a self image and hope that other people see us as we see ourselves. Negative face concern the desire to be us impede in one action, both positive and negative face are” emotionally invested” (brown positive and Levinson 1987).Based on an empirically tested categorization, it is identified by the Singh (1988) that there are three types of complaining private action, third party action, behavior voice, and for the most part refer to the complain behavior directed toward the offending party. A customer who deal with a retailer or manufacture, whether in writing of the consumer or by telephone would be exhibiting voice third party action, on the other hand refer to complain express to party outside not directly involve with the wrong service provider. Customers who contact consumer protection agencies, lawyers, or newspaper as a result of dissatisfying experience with a retailer/dealers or service suppliers a taking third party action. Private action refers to behavior in which customer friends and family not to use that service provider and deciding not to purchase from them again (Singh, 1988). Many experiences to the proclivity to engage in these complaining behaviors have been identified including industry,culture demographics such as age and gender (liu et al.,1996), prior on consumer expectation and experience (Huppert's et al., 2003), the cause for product or service failure (Folkes et al., 1987). In addition, richens (1983) done a study that at the same time considering associations ways and complaining behavior. It was conducted with its interest in and examined what can be considered the boom to voice complaints before that development of the Singh taxonomy. Also this research measured relationship between all three ways of complaining behavior and a particular interaction style. The choice of politeness is measure according to the complaining behaviour. Complaining intimidating act to the degree that a consumer does not want to insult another, he will not engage in complaining behavior. There and huge reasons that's are responsible for the insult of any person that given experiences was dissatisfied and he would

be defending his on face by complaining. A customer will not go for the further complains with the fear of having further insult if he believes that retailer will not take his complains serious or may refuse to take the appropriate actions to correct it . As such it is hypothesizing.

H3. Complaining behavior decreases as a tendency to be polite increase.

A customer seeking to minimize face damage unless or until the complain is not directly record direct confirmation with the service that is provided.

H4.As the propensity of politeness increases the use of voice as complaining behavior decrease.

Although third party actions are less direct than voice complaint. There a customer does not directly communicate with the service provider this type of complaining behavior in some sort of public condom nation (e.g. lawsuit, bad press etc). Such third party action damage the following hypothesis in this position.

H5. As a propensity to polite increase, the use of third party action as the complaining behavior decrease.

Unlike voice compliant and third party action, private action and internally oriented through private action a customer can expressed his/her dissatisfaction without directly confronting to the service provider. It is expected that consumer will take private action independent of the prosperity to be polite.

H6. The use of the private actions uncorrelated with the propensity to be polite

As it has been advised that the least threatening of the three complaining behavior is the private action because without facing public humiliated a customer can expressed disenchantment to the service provider and the voice should be threatening since it direct conflict b/w customer and service provider. Even if the third party action may have several upshot for a service provider then voice complaint a customer does not engaged in direct confrontation will recall from politeness theory that people define their face when threaten by offending the face of other party within the retailer setting for example a manager listening to a customer complaint about the product may tell the customer that he fails to see problems.

H7. The customer will do private action must often followed by third party action and then voice as the tendency to be polite increase.

Ccb(customer complaining behavior)

Figure 1. Proposed Model

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

SAMPLE/DATA:

IN order to collect data for understanding the situation about customer complaining behaviour,a sample of 150 respondents will ask to participate in a self-administered questionnaire. The population for the current research is customer of almaidia in (bwp) Pakistan.the current study utilizes a non-probability sampling technique that is convenience sampling. Convenience sampling is a sampling technique that obtains and collects the relevant information from the sample or the unit of the study that are conveniently available (zikmund,1997).convenience sampling is normally used for collecting a large number of completed surveys speedily and with economy(lym et al.,2010) It has ensured that the sample members posses two main qualification to participates in the self-administered survey. First, the sample member should be almaidia customer and having enough knowledge about almaidia. Second, they never buy any deal other than almaidia because in the case of experience regarding almaidia , it definitely influences the attitude and behavior of the respondent. We select these sample members from (iub)Pakistan. The main target group to collect the sample data are university students. The selection of students is based on the previous results of the studies on customer complaining behaviour.

Measures and scales

The survey instrument of the current study address two major purposes, first is to analyze the relationship of different variables with ccb .second, to collect information about the different characteristics of the respondents that can be used to understand the variations in different categories. The sur-

Loyalty

Voice

vey instrument contains two sections. Section 1 includes different personal and demographic variables. This section will obtain the respondent's information about gender, age, income, education, status, frequency of ccb and possible product to be purchased in the future. Section 2 includes the latent variables that are important current study. These variables includes politeness, attitude, loyalty towards ccb. This section of the is developed based on past literature and already used questionnaires. The scales of study were adopted from the previous literature and published studise.

The questionnaire was distributed among 150 respondents in BAHAWALPUR. These respondents are selected based on the criteria above mentioned. Before giving the questionnaire. The purpose of study and questions were explained to the respondents so they can easily fill the questionnaire with relevant responses. A total of 141 questionnaires were selected and rest 0f the questionnaires was not included in the further analysis due incomplete or invalid responses. After collecting the completed questionnaires, these questionnaires were coded and entered into SPSS sheet.

Procedure

Reliability analysis

Overall cronbach's alpha of the variables or more then acceptable and recommended value 0.50 by nunnally (1970) and 0.60 by moss et al.(1998). This shows that all the 23 items were reliable and valid to measure the opinions of consumers towards customer complaining behavior.

Reliability Statistics		
	Cronbach's Alpha	NO of Items
VOICE RE-SPONSE	.492	3
PRIVATE RE-SPONSE	.859	4
THIRD PARTY RESPONSE	.717	3
LOYALTY	.587	3
ATTITUDE TOWARDS COMPLAINTS	.569	4
POLITENESS	.552	6

Result and analysis

Profile of the respondents Personal and demographic information such as gender, age, income, education, level, status, frequency of internet use and potential purchase over the internet are presented in the following table (table)

Variable	Category	frequency	percentage
Gender	MALE	61	43.3
	FEMALE	80	56.7
Age	15-20 years	23	16.3
	20-25 years	105	74.5
	30-35 years	10	7.1

	35-40 years	3	2.1
education	Bachelor	31	22.0
	Master	81	57.4
	Ms/M.phill	26	18.4
	PHD	3	2.1
Income	Below 15000	96	68.1
	15000-25000		
	25000-35000	14	9.9
	35000-45000	11	7.8
		20	14.2
Status	Student	126	89.4
	Employed	9	6.4
	Businessman	6	4.3

Hypothesis testing

1. Customer loyalty:

According to the result of the study, non-significant relationship between loyalty and ccb with $(B=-0.10)$ and $(p<0.05)$ according to these results, loyalty -10% in ccb. These result supports H1.

2. Attitude:

Significant relationship between attitude and ccb with $(B=.308)$ and $(P>0.05)$ results suggest that attitude contribute more than 30% to ccb. these result of the study validate H2.

3. Politeness:

Significant relationship between polite and ccb with $(B=.276)$ and $(P>0.05)$ results suggest that polite contribute more than 27% to ccb this result of the study support H3.

Politeness and voice response:

Significant relationship between politeness and voice response with (B=0.321) and (p<0.05) voice response contributes more than 32% In politeness. The results support H4.

Politeness and thirdparty response:

Significant relationship between politeness and third party response with (B=0.210)and (p<0.05) third party response contributes 21% In politeness. The results of the study support H5.

Politeness private response:

No significant relationship between private response and politeness with (B=0.113) and (p<0.05) according to these results, private response contribute more than 11% in politeness. The result of the study support H6.

Politeness, voice, private action and 3 rd party response:

There is a significant relationship between politeness with voice and private action but the 3rd party response show non significant relationship with politeness. These results support H7.

HY- POTH ESIS	MODEL VARIABLES	Unstandardized Coef- ficients		Standard- ized Coef- ficients	Critical Region	p	P
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Results
H1	customer Loyalty → CCB	-.008	.072	-.010	-.112	.911	NON.SIGNIFICANT
H2	Attitude → CCB	.308	.081	.308	3.820	.000	SIGNIFICANT
H3	politeness → CCB	.335	.099	.276	3.383	.001	SIGNIFICANT
H4	Voice Response → CCB	.213	.053	.321	3.996	.000	SIGNIFICANT
H5	Private Response → CCB	.062	.046	.113	1.346	.181	NON.SIGNIFICANT

H6	3rd party response → CCB →	.123	.048	.210	2.534	.012	SIGNIFICANT
H7							

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSIONS

The complaining behavior choice depends, on the consumer’s politeness. Impolite customers use voice more likely than polite consumers. The impolite customers having equal chances to use third-party actions. Some survey’s design have satisfaction may also lacking for hopeful voice. Some questions may more successfully bring out customer complaints than generalized questions; above all customers do not want to be unfair. Managers may probably consider positive politeness a way to seek complaints. Positive politeness express a support of the other person’s wants and conveys a sense of similarity and unity. A service provider makes a point to identify the chance of displeasure, or a less perfect skill, and a wish to diminish such incidence. The managers will have to work hard to identify those customers voiced complaints with potential to act accordingly. In marketing literature the role of effective complaint management on customer loyalty is a current subject. researches effect of the service recovery (explaining, communication, feedback, and redress) on perceived justice and customer loyalty. On the other hand the effect of customer loyalty on complaint behaviour is not taken similar attention. Assert that loyal customers who experienced dissatisfaction tend to complain more often than non-loyal .It can be claimed that loyal customers prefer to solve their problems with firm instead of leaving firm immediately .So customer loyalty is researched under the scope of this study. In 1970 it is documented by Hirschman that the significance of attitude to complaining for accommodating complaint and exit behavior.it is found that attitude toward complaining is a essential variable in the prediction of complaint behavior that a positive attitude to complaining increased the possibility that the students would complain to other .In 1982 Richins study attitude to complaining and recommended that the attitude involve individual’s personal norms about complaining, the net benefit of complaining and the perceptions of community benefits that will result as of complaining. Grace et al. (2006) when making a complaint there is an unwillingness to complain with a lack of confidence, perceptions of risk in regard to public complaining and feeling rough. It ought to be highlighted that even though polite customers have fewer voice complaints than impolite customers, it does not mean

that they not at all do so. Moreover; it is expected that investigate the conditions under which polite customers do and do not use voice complaints. The advance researchers may also attempt to discover to tackle some of the methodological and abstract boundaries of the in progress study. To develop the definition of politeness A try was made which consist of non-verbal as well as verbal behavior,All the items which are in the politeness scale related to the indirect nature of expression .The researcher may further seek to build up this scale by adding more items to this feature of verbal behavior.

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